

INTERFACIAL FRACTURE TOUGHNESS MEASUREMENT AND IMPROVEMENT FOR COMPOSITE/METAL INTERFACES

W.S. Kim and J.J. Lee

Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology
Dept. Mechanical Engineering, KAIST, Daejeon, 305-701, South Korea
goodman@kaist.ac.kr and leejungju@kaist.ac.kr

SUMMARY

The present study is concerned with the strength evaluation and improvement for composite/metal interfaces. Interfacial fracture toughness was measured over a wide range of mode-mixities. Mechanical interlocking effect on adhesion strength is elucidated by using micro-patterns and linking adhesion strength to microscopic failure mechanisms.

Keywords: adhesion strength, mixed-mode fracture, mechanical interlocking

INTRODUCTION

Adhesive bonding is enlarging its application range as a practical method for the joining of dissimilar materials in automotives, aircrafts, microelectronics and medical devices industries replacing conventional joining techniques such as welding, bolting and riveting [1-5]. Especially for joining of fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) composites to other structural materials such as metal, traditional joining techniques can be inapplicable or susceptible to damage. However, adhesive-bonding can be used for many types of adherend materials and does not cause property degradation, since machining for hole fabrication for riveting or melting-point heating for welding are not required. One of the predominant concerns for engineers in using adhesive bonding is to optimize the adhesion strength. Understanding adhesion mechanisms and theoretical investigation of the influence of each mechanism on adhesion strength can fundamentally allow us to reach the formation of strong and reliable adhesive joints. The purpose of the present work is to investigate the effects of loading mode and mechanical interlocking on the adhesion strength of metal-polymer interfaces. In order to link the microscopic adhesion phenomenon to the macroscopic adhesion strength of a bonded joint, fracture mechanics concept has been utilized, and adhesion strength is measured as the required energy for fracture, i.e. the interfacial toughness.

Theories of adhesion for the composite/metal interface are considered in the following section. Experiments have been carried out with composite/metal bonded specimens to measure the fracture energy a composite/metal interface. Micro line-patterns were fabricated on the steel plate prior to bonding to elucidate the effect of metal surface morphology on the interface strength. The results are reported in subsequent sections and discussed in the view point of fracture energetics.

ADHESION MECHANISMS FOR COMPOSITE/METAL INTERFACES

Among a number of mechanisms that account for the adhesion phenomenon, adsorption and mechanical interlocking are the predominant theories that contribute to the adhesion strength of metal-polymer interfaces [1-4]. As schematically described in Fig. 1, adhesive force exists between metal and polymer induced by intermolecular attractions provided molecular-scale intimate contact is achieved (Fig. 1(a)), and the penetration of the polymer into craters and pores in rough metal substrates enhances the bond strength through mechanical interlocking (Fig. 1(b)). Chemical bonding can also be introduced as a dominant adhesion strength enhancement factor by embedding a coupling agent at the interface and forming a metal/coupling agent/polymer system [6,7]. In this study, interest is in the investigation of the cause of adhesion strength by elucidating energy-expending mechanisms for fracture rather than adhesion strength enhancement. Hence, special surface treatment was not performed to form chemical bonds at the metal-polymer interface; consequently, adsorption and mechanical interlocking effects were focused in the present study. Quantitatively, adsorption effect can be measured as the thermodynamic work of adhesion, W_a , between the two media, and mechanical interlocking effect has been considered to cause viscoelastic and plastic energy dissipation in the polymer adhesive material during crack propagation but has not been measured in a direct microscopic manner. From the pioneering work to the present, researchers have tried to correlate the theoretical work of adhesion with the measured adhesive joint strength [8-11].

Fig. 1 Schematics of the polymer/metal adhesion.

It is well-known that the thermodynamic work of adhesion is far below than the practical bond strength; however, the work of adhesion is regarded to play a vital role in adhesion so that small changes in its value can cause large changes in the practical adhesion strength. Many studies devoted to measuring adhesion suggested that the greater values of the practical work of fracture compared to the work of adhesion can be explained by taking the plastic deformation of the adhesive layer or substrates into consideration. In this paper, the separation energy of a metal-polymer adhesion is evaluated in terms of the work of adhesion, work of cohesion and plastic dissipation. The emphasis is on the quantification of each energy dissipation mechanisms and the investigation of the effect of the interaction among the material properties of polymer, surface morphology of metal, and loading modes on the fracture resisting mechanisms of metal-polymer interfaces. This approach allows us to explain the wide range of

adhesion strengths observed depending on loading mode and the surface morphology of metal substrates.

MIXED-MODE INTERFACIAL TOUGHNESS MEASUREMENT

A number of test methods have been suggested to measure interfacial fracture toughness over various ratios of mode I to mode II loadings [12,13]. The single-leg bending (SLB) test, which was first proposed by Yoon and Hong [14] for the determination of mixed-mode delamination toughness for composites and rigorously analyzed to investigate its suitability for determining interface fracture toughness by Davidson and Sundararaman [15], has significant advantage. As shown in Fig. 2, the geometry and loading condition of the SLB specimen is very simple. Due to the simple beam type geometry, the total energy release rate is calculated using beam theory and partitioned into the mode I and mode II components.

Fig. 2 Schematic diagram of the composite/steel SLB test.

$$G_I = \frac{P^2 a^2}{8B^2} \left(\frac{D_2^2}{(D_1 + D_2)^2} \left(\frac{1}{D_1} + \frac{1}{D_2} \right) \right) \quad (1)$$

$$G_{II} = \frac{P^2 a^2}{8B^2} \left(\frac{1}{(D_1 + D_2)} - \frac{1}{D} \right) \quad (2)$$

Here, D_1 denotes the flexural rigidity of the upper beam, D_2 is the flexural rigidity of the lower beam ($D_i = E_i I_i$ for plane stress and $D_i = E_i I_i / (1 - \nu_i^2)$ for plane strain condition), and D is the effective flexural rigidity of the bonded beam section. P is the applied load, a is the crack length, and B is the width of a specimen. Total energy release rate G is the sum of the mode I and mode II components. By changing the thickness ratio of the upper and lower beam, various mode-mixities can be accomplished.

$$G = \frac{1}{2w} \left(\frac{M_1^2}{D_1} + \frac{M_2^2}{D_2} - \frac{M^2}{D} \right) = \frac{P^2 a^2}{8B^2} \left(\frac{1}{D_1} - \frac{1}{D} \right) = G_I + G_{II} \quad (3)$$

The failure locus obtained from several specimens with different thicknesses is shown in Fig. 3. A mixed-mode failure criterion of the used composite/metal interface is proposed by linear interpolation as Eq. (4). The critical fracture toughness in mode II loading ($G_{IIc} = 280 \text{ J/m}^2$) is larger than that of mode I ($G_{Ic} = 140 \text{ J/m}^2$) by two times.

Fig. 3 The failure locus of a composite/steel interface.

$$\frac{G_I}{G_{Ic}} + \frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIc}} = \frac{G_I}{140} + \frac{G_{II}}{280} = 1 \quad (4)$$

SURFACE AND INTERFACE CHARACTERIZATION AND OBSERVATION

The topography of a surface is a kind of random data which requires a statistical analysis for the determination of characteristic parameters. However, if a surface topography is designed and fabricated into a patterned structure, a surface can be completely characterized with several parameters. The surface parameters facilitate the investigation of how the morphological changes of the surface influence the adhesion strength. Conventional photolithography along with wet-etching was utilized to fabricate micro line-patterns on the steel surface (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4 Schematic diagram of the micro line-patterned steel specimen.

After the surface patterning process, CFRP prepregs (USN-150 supplied by SK chemical, Korea) were laminated on steel plates ([0₉/steel]) and bonded by undergoing the standard curing process of the CFRP prepreg. In other words, composite/metal joint specimens were bonded through the co-cure bonding process.

The micro line-patterns, which were fabricated on the steel plate prior to bonding, were created perpendicular to the direction of crack propagation. The effect of metal surface morphology on the interface strength was assessed by varying the width, depth and spacing of micro-line patterns on the steel surface. The line-patterned surface morphology can be completely characterized by three independent parameters. Three parameters were chosen as R : excavated line depth, which corresponds to conventional definition of surface roughness, w_1 : excavated line width, w_2 : preserved line width (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5 Schematics of micro line-patterned steel/polymer interfaces.

In the first place, the three surface characterizing parameters were varied in a congruent manner as shown in Fig. 3 to investigate roughness effect only. Using the congruent geometry set of surfaces, the aspect ratios (w_1/R , w_2/R) and the roughness factor (the ratio of real contact area to nominal area, $A_{\text{real}}/A_{\text{nom}}$), which were reported to have strong effects on adhesion strength as surface geometry parameters [16-18], can be maintained as constant. Control samples were also produced with fine-polished smooth steel surface without patterns.

Figure 6 shows SEM images of micro line-patterned steel surfaces. Unlike the initial design target of the line pattern, the cross section of the grooves was semicircular due to the wet-etching process applied to the steel, an isotropic material. The three surface parameters were modified while maintaining its original meaning (Fig. 6). Due to the isotropic wet-etching process, surface parameters maintain a relationship of $R/w_1 = 0.5$. The widths of line patterns, both w_1 and w_2 on steel substrates were varied by using different masks in the process of photolithography and controlling etching time. The width of etched line, w_1 ranged from 10 to 90 μm with its maximum thickness, R ranging from 5 to 45 μm . Figure 7 shows optical microscope cross-sectional images of a metal/composite bonded interface. The epoxy resin, which was extracted from the CFRP prepreg during its curing process, has completely filled up the micro grooves on the steel surface. Therefore, the mechanical keying, or interlocking, of the polymer into the steel surface irregularities has completely attained in the micro-line patterned steel-CFRP interface.

Fig. 6 SEM micrographs of line-patterned steel surfaces.

Fig. 7 Optical micrographs of line-patterned steel/composite interfaces.

INTERFACIAL TOUGHNESS IMPROVEMENT USING SURFACE TOPOGRAPHY MODIFICATION

The interfacial fracture toughness, G_C which is the mechanical energy per unit interfacial area at which fracture occurs, was measured as the adhesion strength of the steel/composite interface. A bi-material end-notched flexure (ENF) test, which provides a pure mode II loading condition were utilized. Figures 8 and 9 show the schematics and picture of the bi-material ENF test setup used for the measurement of interface fracture energies. The thickness ratio of the bi-material ENF specimen was held constant at $h_1/h_2=1.25$ to locate the neutral axis of the bonded beam at the interface. The miniaturized micro-bend tester was set up using a computer-controlled stepper motor, and the testing was performed under displacement control at a ramp rate of $10\mu\text{m}/\text{sec}$. Both load and displacement data were recorded digitally using an interfaced computer.

Fig. 8 Schematic diagram of the bi-material (composite/steel) ENF test.

Fig. 9 Three-point bend test of a bi-material (composite/steel) ENF specimen.

Typical load-displacement curves obtained from ENF tests is presented in Fig. 10. As most ductile materials, there is a gradual transition from elastic to inelastic, non-linear behavior, and the point at which crack propagation begins is hard to define. It can be seen that the failure load of adhesive joints increase according to the increase of the excavated width (w_1) of the line-pattern.

Fig. 10 load-displacement curves from ENF tests with different pattern width ratios.

Fracture surfaces were observed using optical and scanning electron microscopes. As seen in Fig. 11, the excavated region on steel surfaces shows pure cohesive failure and the preserved region on steel surfaces shows pure interfacial failure mode. The cause of high interfacial toughness of specimens having large pattern width (w_1) can be explained by the increase of cohesive failure mode fraction. Cohesive failure, caused from the molecular decohesion of the polymer resin, expends larger energy for crack propagation than interfacial failure. Furthermore, plastic dissipation in the bulk polymer material is effectively-induced during the crack growth in the polymer region rather than during the crack growth at the interface. SEM micrograph of a composite/steel interface after crack propagation shows that crack growth causes plastic damages in polymer resins both the interfacial and cohesive failure region (Fig. 12).

Fig. 11 SEM micrographs of fracture surfaces on the patterned steel side for different pattern width ratios (a) $w_1/(w_1 + w_2)=1/2$ (b) $w_1/(w_1 + w_2)=1/8$.

Fig. 12 SEM micrograph of a composite/steel interface after crack propagation.

In order to analyze fracture energetics by decomposing the interfacial toughness into the work of adhesion, work of cohesion and plastic dissipation, the width ratio λ defined as $\lambda = w_1/(w_1 + w_2)$ was introduced. The variation of the measured interfacial toughness, G_{IIc} according to the width ratio, λ is presented in Fig. 13.

Fig. 13 Interfacial fracture toughness, G_{IIc} , as a function of micro-pattern width.

Fig. 14 Schematics of failure modes: (a) interfacial; (b) cohesive; (c) partial cohesive.

As schematically shown in Fig. 14, interfacial failure requires the work of adhesion (Eq. (5)), and cohesive failure requires the work of cohesion (Eq. (6)).

$$W_a = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 - \gamma_{12} \quad (5)$$

$$W_c = 2\gamma_1 \quad (6)$$

where γ_1 , γ_2 and γ_{12} are the surface free energies of the phase 1, 2 and the energy of an interface between phases 1 and 2. For the case of partial cohesive failure, both work of adhesion and cohesion terms are needed to constitute the practical work of fracture, W_p .

$$W_p = \lambda W_i + (1 - \lambda) W_c \quad (7)$$

CONCLUSIONS

The present study was carried out to estimate experimentally, the effect of loading mode and mechanical interlocking on the adhesion strength of composite/metal interfaces. The interfacial fracture toughness G_c , which is the mechanical energy per unit interfacial area at which fracture occurs, was measured according to various loading mode and surface pattern geometry. The obtained results allow us to attain the following conclusions

- The composite/metal interfacial fracture toughness G_c is a function of the loading mode. The increase of G_c according to the increase of mode-mixity results from the failure mode transition from interfacial to cohesive.
- The molecular dissipation of the polymer is a predominant factor that attributes to the total fracture energy and is the source of the dependence of adhesion strength on loading mode.

- The amount of molecular dissipation of the polymer is determined by the interface geometry of the metal-polymer bonding, thus the adhesion strength of a metal-polymer interface is controlled by the interaction of the two principal adhesion mechanisms, the adsorption and mechanical interlocking.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Korea Science and Engineering Foundation (KOSEF) grant funded by the Korea government (MOST) (No. R01-2007-000-20655-0)

References

1. A. J. Kinloch, *Adhesion and Adhesives: Science and Technology*, Chapman and Hall, New York, 1987.
2. D.E. Packham, *Handbook of Adhesion*. Longman, UK 1992.
3. A. Pizzi and K. L. Mittal (Ed.), *Handbook of Adhesive Technology*, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1994.
4. A. V. Pocius, *Adhesion and Adhesives Technology: An Introduction* Hanser, New York, 1997.
5. B. G. Yacobia, S. Martin, K. Davis, A. Hudson, and M. Hubertb, *J. Appl. Phys.*, Vol. 91 (2002), 6227.
6. E. P. Plueddemann, *Silane Coupling Agents*, 2nd ed, Plenum Press, New York, 1991.
7. K. L. Mittal (Ed.), *Silanes and Other Coupling Agents*. VSP, Utrecht, 1992.
8. D.H. Kaelble, *J. Adhesion* Vol. 1 (1969), 102.
9. E.H. Andrews and A.J. Kinloch, *Proc. Roy. Soc.* Vol. A-332 (1973), 385.
10. K.L. Mittal, *Polym Eng. Sci.* Vol. 17 (1977), 467.
11. D.E. Packham, *Int. J. Adhes. Adhes.* Vol. 13 (1993), 67.
12. P.G. Charalambides, J. Lund, A.G. Evans and R.M. McMeeking, *J. Appl. Mech.* Vol. 56 (1989), 77.
13. J.S. Wang and Z. Suo, *Acta metall mater.* Vol. 38 (1990), 1279.
14. S.H. Yoon and C.S. Hong, *Int. J. Fract.* Vol. 43 (1990), R3.
15. B.D. Davidson and V. Sundararaman, *Int. J. Fract.* Vol. 78 (1996), 193.
16. D.E. Packham, *Int. J. Adhes. Adhes.* Vol. 23 (2003), 437.
17. S.G. Prolongo, G. Rosario and A. Urena, *J. Adhesion Sci. Technol.*, Vol. 20 (2006), 457.
18. Z.X. Jiang, Y.D. Huang, L. Liu and J. Long, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* Vol. 253 (2007), 9357.